

Main Characteristics of the Accommodation Facilities in Rural Areas: The Case Study of Bulgarian North-West Region

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ABSTRACT

Tourism sector is very important for the Bulgarian economy. Before the pandemic of COVID-19 it generates between 10% and 12% of the country's GDP. The present paper discusses the specifics of the tourism business in the rural areas. For the purpose of the study the research object are the accommodation facilities in these areas. The North-West Region of Bulgaria is chosen as a researched area because it is the least economically developed area in the country. There are 46 rural areas, evenly distributed in the five provinces of the region. The main types of accommodation, their characteristics, their territorial location compared to major urban centers and their relationship with the number of tourist attractions in the researched areas are identified. The main goal of the paper is to explore the potential for development of tourism in rural areas, based on a study of the accommodation facilities in the rural areas in the North-West Region of Bulgaria. The research includes an analysis of the disparities between the different rural areas, the possible reasons for them, as well as the opportunities for tourism development. The conclusions that have been made can become the basis for the development of tourism products and regional strategies for the development of specialized and alternative types of tourism.

1. Introduction

Until the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic, tourism was one of the most developed economic activities in the world economy. According to the UN World Tourism Organization and the World Trade Organization, in 2019 it accounted for 7% of world trade, ranking third only after trade in fuels and chemical products and before the automotive and food industries (UNWTO, 2020). In Bulgaria in the period 2010-2019 tourism generates between 10% and 12% of the country's GDP. It accounts for over 40% of total exports of services. It forms 11-12% of the total exports of the country. This report looks at the North-West Region in the context of tourism. It is one of the six regions and has the least developed economy in the country. There is a common understanding among researchers and scholars that rural areas are territories where development is generally lagging behind the rest of the country. They are characterized by deteriorated demographic and economic characteristics as

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poverty, unemployment, depopulation of the territories, deterioration of the age and educational structure, etc. (Ilieva, 2018; Terziyska, 2018). The study and analysis of several rural development aspects (demographic situation, economic and social development, human capital, infrastructure security, etc.) can be used to take practical measures in the context of planning, programming and management of territorial development. The study of a spatial unit in terms of its potential for social and economic development requires an analysis and assessment of both the quantitative and qualitative aspects of the resources at its disposal (Georgieva, 2019). Rural areas are important because they are part of the cultural and historical heritage of communities and because they concentrate the vast majority of the country's natural resources. Modern theories of rural development emphasize the model of development of these areas, based on their natural resources and strengths, which will lead to sustainability of this development. The strengths of the rural areas are the conditions for agriculture, their natural resources (water, air, environment), landmarks, cultural heritage and opportunities for sustainable rural tourism. The purpose of the present paper is to identify the potential for the development of tourism in rural municipalities as a tool for overcoming economic backwardness, revitalization and overcoming the demographic problem. The territorial scope of the present study includes the rural municipalities of the five districts of the North-West Region - Vidin, Vratsa, Montana, Pleven and Lovech. For this purpose, the number of the accommodation facilities, their types and spatial distribution are analyzed. Conclusions about the possible reasons for the differences between them are made. The disclosure of regional disparities at different territorial levels and the comparative studies provide an opportunity to systematize a significant amount of information, conduct comprehensive studies, obtain adequate assessments, support the implementation of regional policy and develop management strategies. The dynamic changes during the development of the country require the development and testing of new models for assessment, organization and management of the national territory and its regions. One of the biggest issues in formulating the concept of rural development is related to the definition and delineation of these areas. Therefore, in order to achieve the main goal of the paper, current issues related to the definition of the rural areas in the national and world scientific literature and the basic concepts for their typology are considered. The limitations for performing analyzes in relation to the data collected by the National Statistical Institute are outlined.

2. Literature Review

The literature review covers scientific publications, research papers, official documents of the EU, the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) and the United Nations, as well as the existing legislation in Bulgaria relating to rural areas.

For the first time in 1975, the World Bank publishes a report on rural issues entitled Rural Development (World Bank, 1975). The report states that rural

development must become a strategy that addresses three main issues: (1) increasing the productivity of the rural economy and the entry of modern productions; (2) poverty reduction; (3) improving the quality of life in rural areas through the use of available resources. Rural development is part of the policies of the countries, and the purpose of this development is to achieve a territorial balance that creates equal opportunities for life, work and personal fulfillment of people living in cities and villages.

The review found that there is currently no common understanding of the term rural area and it is still being discussed and developed (Dasgupta et al., 2014; Li et al., 2019). For example, in EU Member States there are different definitions of areas that are called rural. Each country adopts its own national criteria (Dimitrovski et al., 2012; Carson et al., 2014; Prestholdt & Nordbø, 2015). OECD (1994) points out that the delineation of rural areas in the various Member States most often takes into account three main aspects, on the basis of which the relevant definition is formulated. These are:

- the size of the territorial units and the respective hierarchical level in the territorial structure;
- the criteria used to characterize the territorial units at the respective levels;
- the quantitative thresholds applied to determine the border between rural and other areas.

Bulgaria does not have long experience in planning and implementing a special policy aimed at rural development. The main issues and problems related to these areas are considered as part of the overall territorial planning and development of the country (Popov, 2007). For the purposes of regional development policy in the 1990s, some rural areas were identified as backward. In accordance with the Regional Development Act of 1999, the Decree of the Council of Ministers № 105 of 2 June 1999 adopted an Ordinance on the criteria for determining the areas for targeted impact and their territorial scope (promulgated SG, iss. 53 of 11 June 1999, repealed, SG No. 64 of 23 July 2004). The backward rural areas in Bulgaria are defined as one of the types of regions with specific problems and priorities. The document states that backward rural areas include municipalities or groups of municipalities with a predominant rural lifestyle, specializing in agriculture and forestry, with low levels of economic development, underdeveloped technical infrastructure and skills of the workforce, with acute social problems, such as high unemployment, low per capita income and depopulation. The municipalities included in backward rural areas are determined on the basis of the following criteria:

- 1) Lack of a medium, large or very large city in the region - the largest city in the region has a population of less than 30,000 people;
- 2) The revenues from activity on the territory of the municipality per capita for two of the last three consecutive years amount to no more than 30% of the average level for the country for the respective year;
- 3) The average unemployment rate for the last two consecutive years must be above 50% of the national average for the year in question;

4) Population density to be below 75% of the national average, measured in population per square km;

5) The relative share of agricultural or forest areas must exceed by 20% the relative average for the country;

6) The relative share of employees in agriculture and forestry in the total number of employees should be over 20% of the national average for the previous year.

Municipalities in backward rural areas must meet the first three criteria and at least one of the others.

A new Ordinance, adopted by Decree of the Council of Ministers № 166 of 14 July 2004, determines the indicators for delimitation of regions for targeted impact (promulgated in SG, issue 64 of 23 July 2004). The indicators for determining each type of area are quantitative measures of the criteria. Their values for each municipality are compared with the defined threshold values provided in the Ordinance, in order to include in or exclude the municipality from a specific type of region for targeted impact. A backward rural area means “an area in which the majority of the working population is employed in agriculture and forestry, characterized by a low level of development of transport, technical and social infrastructure, low qualification of the working age population, limited employment opportunities, high unemployment, low incomes and depopulation”. The territorial scope of the region is determined by the following specific indicators:

- share of employed persons in agricultural holdings over 20% of the national average according to the 2003 census data;
- net income per capita below 50% compared to the national average for the last 3 years;
- average unemployment rate over 25% compared to the national average for the last 3 years;
- share of persons with lower than secondary education over 20% compared to the national average;
- age dependency ratio over 25% of the national average for the last 3 years;
- population density less than 70 people per sq. km;
- more than 70% of the population does not fall into the area of a motorway and / or a class I road (20 km from a motorway or 10 km from a class I road);
- more than 10% of the population uses drinking water with a deviation in quality, accepted as a standard for the country for the last 3 years;
- more than 10% of the population uses water with a regime in the water supply for the last 3 years.

By Decree of the Council of Ministers № 30 of 15.02.2008 in another Ordinance are determined the criteria for the less-favored regions and their territorial scope (promulgated, SG, issue 20 of 26.02.2008, amended and supplemented, SG, iss. 53 of 12.07.2011). The document lists mountainous areas and restricted areas other than mountainous, as disadvantaged. The second group includes the lands of settlements that have poorly productive agricultural lands. The appendix to this Ordinance lists by name the settlements that fall into this category.

However, the formulation of a formal definition of rural areas is needed in connection with the country's EU membership negotiations. For the implementation of the pre-accession Special Program for Accession in the Field of Agriculture and Rural Development (SAPARD) in the National Plan for Agriculture and Rural Development (2000-2006) a working definition was adopted. It states that rural areas include "municipalities whose largest city has a population of less than 30,000 and a population density of less than 150 inhabitants per square kilometer". Later, in Ordinance №14 of 01.04.2003 of the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry and the Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works, rural areas are defined as municipalities, on the territory of which there is no city with a population of over 30,000 people and the population density is under 150 p./sq. km. The municipality is a basic administrative-territorial unit or "building element", on the basis of which this definition is formulated. The current study uses this definition of rural areas, which is considered official at the moment, although it is formulated too generally and is not in itself a sufficient condition for the successful implementation of measures to address the problems in these areas.

Some researchers in their definitions of rural areas also use municipalities as a basic unit. According to Yankova (2002), rural areas are the territories of municipalities with village centers. According to Geshev (1990), rural areas are territorial units or municipalities with a relatively low density, including villages and small towns with a population of up to 10,000 people.

According to (Simeonov & Petrov, 2007), a sufficient number of indicators need to be used to identify municipalities as rural. The reasons for such a statement are the following:

- By their nature, municipalities are complex, dynamic and open systems. A significant number of indicators should be used for their comprehensive presentation and on this basis their socio-economic development and potential should be assessed;
- Defining the appearance of the municipalities as rural depends on the demographic processes, the economic, environmental, cultural, infrastructural and social conditions, the lifestyle, etc.;
- If we do not take into account the numerous aspects of territorial development, we may end up with a situation where the so-called rural municipalities are at average or above average level of socio-economic development and vice versa, municipalities with relatively good demographic indicators, but with low socio-economic potential to not be included in the list of rural areas.

This arguments impose the need to determine the rural areas based on the maximum possible set of features that characterize the overall complex development of municipalities.

According to Georgieva (2018) in the definitions for delineating the territorial scope of the rural areas at national and international level there are many different definitions of rural areas depending on the specifics of the territory to which they relate and the objectives for which they are formulated. In this sense, these

definitions can be called target or formulated and applied to specific functions. In many cases, even within one country, more than one definition is used. Over different periods of time, national definitions have been the subject of discussions and adjusted to reflect changes in socio-economic conditions or the administrative-territorial structure of the countries.

In this context the rural areas definition is very important for the future of the economics in these territories. Tourism sector is an accelerator of economic growth both at local, regional and national level (Statev, 2009; Kostadinova, 2019) and it is very important to be discussed.

The literature review found that in the last five years, publications related to rural areas and tourism have addressed the following topics: sustainability of rural areas through tourism development (Ibănescu et al., 2018; Khartishvili et al. 2019; Ćurčić et al., 2021; Kataya, 2021); planning, revitalization and tourism (Guo & Sun, 2016; Pato & Kastenholz, 2017; Long et al., 2019); pandemic and rural tourism (Coroş et al., 2021; Robina-Ramírez et al., 2022; Vaishar & Šťastná, 2022) and digitalisation of rural activities (Kumar, 2020; Birnbaum, 2021).

The present paper differs from the others in that it seeks to identify differences in the development of rural tourism in a region. To answer the questions whether there are rural areas without accommodation establishments, ie. without developed tourism? What are the physiographic characteristics of these areas where tourism is concentrated or absent? What is the type of accommodation facilities and does it differ in different rural areas?

3. Methodology

The main goal of the paper is to explore the potential for development of tourism in rural areas, based on a study of the accommodation facilities in the rural areas in the North-West Region of Bulgaria. Several sub-goals have been set to achieve it:

- identification of the rural areas in the region on the basis of the current legislation, using the methods of analysis and synthesis;
- establishing the number of accommodation establishments in the rural areas of the region based on the national tourist register of accommodation facilities by types, municipalities and settlements, maintained by the Ministry of Tourism of Republic of Bulgaria. By using mathematical and statistical methods, the information is processed so that it can be analyzed;
- presentation of the geographical distribution of accommodation establishments in rural areas, using cartographic methods and GIS.

In conclusion, an analysis of the disparities between the different rural areas, the possible reasons for them, as well as the opportunities for tourism development is made.

The main economic activities developed in the North-West Region are the food industry, timber and wood processing industry, battery production, machine building, garment production, pharmaceutical and chemical industry, services. Agriculture has established traditions in this area. The North-West Region remains the region with the lowest economic activity and employment levels, and therefore the highest unemployment. The density of the road network is equal to the national average, with a total length of 3 422 km, which represents 17% of the national road network. It is least developed in Montana Province - 169 km / 1000 sq. km, and best in Vidin Province - 202 km / 1000 sq. km. In the provinces of Lovech and Pleven it is 183 km / 1000 sq. km., and in Vratsa Province is 179 km / 1000 sq. km. There is no functioning airport serving passengers in the North-West Region. Water transport is presented along the Trans-European Transport Corridor № 7, which includes the ports of Vidin, Lom and Oryahovo. The importance of the port of Vidin is related to the operation of four port terminals, and especially the ferry Vidin - Calafat.

The North-West Region is rich in natural and anthropogenic tourist resources. On its territory is located part of one of the two Bulgarian national parks included in the PAN Parks network - Central Balkan National Park (Zhelezov, 2016). As well, there are 32 sites that form part of the initiative of the Bulgarian Tourist Union (BTU) - "100 national tourist sites". 3 883 registered immovable cultural values dating from different historical periods are located there. According to the Register of Immovable Cultural Property with a category of "national importance" in the North-West Region there are 210 sites (National Institute for Immovable Cultural Heritage). In Vidin Province there are 36, in Vratsa Province - 47, in Montana Province - 32, in Pleven Province - 29 and in Lovech Province - 66. There are no sites included in the UNESCO World Heritage List in the North-West Region. Nowadays, three sites on the territory of the region are part of the proposals for inclusion in this list, appearing in the indicative lists of natural and cultural sites in Bulgaria. These are the Magura Cave with drawings from the Bronze Age - included in 1984 in the indicative list of cultural sites in Bulgaria, and Vratsa Karst Reserve with natural landmark Belogradchik Rocks (both sites included in 1984), part of the indicative list of natural sites of Bulgaria.

There are four elements in the National Representative List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage "Living Human Treasures – Bulgaria" (Ministry of Culture, 2021) in the North-West Region:

- In the field of Intangible Cultural Heritage "Traditional rites and holidays" - the project "Kalusha - ancient rite, preserved for generations" preserved by the National Community Center "Nikola Y. Vaptsarov", the village of Harlets, Kozloduy Municipality, Vratsa Province, performed by the group for authentic folklore "Kalushari";

- In the field of Intangible Cultural Heritage "Traditional crafts, home activities and livelihoods / Armament" - the project "Dyanko Dyankov - the master of ancient weapons from the town of Apriltsi", preserved by National Community Center "Prosveta" - Apriltsi village and Museum of Folk Arts and Crafts town of Troyan,

Lovech Province, performed by Dyanko Dyankov (gunsmith, knife maker, tin maker);

- In the field of Intangible Cultural Heritage “Traditional crafts, household activities and livelihoods - carpet weaving” - the project “Chiprovtsi carpets”, preserved by National Community Center “Petar Bogdan – 1909”, the town of Chiprovtsi, Montana Province, performed by Women’s Folklore Group (Ivanka Ivaylova and Zaharinka Ivaylova);

- In the field of Intangible Cultural Heritage “Traditional singing and playing” - the project “Preserving the Danube rhythms in the village of Antimovo”, preserved by National Community Center “Development – 1926”, Antimovo village, Vidin Municipality, Vidin Province, performed by wind music “Danube rhythms”.

There are a total of 854 accommodation establishments in the rural areas of the North-West Region. Over 70% of them are in Lovech Province.

Fig. 2. Accommodation establishments in the rural areas in North-West Region by provinces

Source: Authors’ calculations

Primary data: <https://ntr.tourism.government.bg/CategoryzationAll.nsf/mn.xsp>

According to the Tourism Act of Republic of Bulgaria (2021), accommodation establishments are divided into the following main categories:

- Class A - hotels, motels, apartment tourist complexes, holiday villages, tourist villages and villas;
- Class B - family hotels, hostels, pensions, corporate lodging, guest houses, bungalows and campsites;
- Class C - guest rooms and guest apartments.

There are 10 306 beds in the rural areas of the North-West Region. 58% of them are class B accommodation establishments, 27% - class A and 15% - class C. In class B predominates beds in guest houses (3 392) and family hotel beds (1 794).

4.1. Tourism in the rural areas in Lovech Province

Lovech Province has an area of 4132 sq. km. 79% of them are rural areas. It is located on the northern slopes of the Central Balkan Mountains, the central Fore-Balkans, part of the Devetashko plateau and the Danube plain. It includes 110

settlements - 8 cities (Lovech, Troyan, Teteven, Apriltsi, Lukovit, Ugarchin, Letnitsa and Yablanitsa) and 102 villages. There are eight municipalities and only Lovech is an urban one. The rural areas include the other seven municipalities - Apriltsi, Letnitsa, Lukovit, Teteven, Troyan, Ugarchin and Yablanitsa.

In 2022 in the rural areas of Lovech Province there are 512 registered accommodation establishments with a total of 6 934 beds. They are divided into 11 categories. Their territorial distribution is shown on Fig. 3:

Fig. 3. Map of the rural areas in Lovech Province

Over 85% of the beds in the accommodation establishments are in the mountainous rural areas - Troyan Municipality (2 494), Teteven Municipality (2015) and Apriltsi Municipality (1500). The group of the high-category accommodation facilities is represented by the four-star hotel Olympus in Teteven, Troyan Plaza in Troyan and Diplomat Plaza Hotel and Resort in Lukovit and the five-star eco-complex Sunny House in Apriltsi.

4.1.1. Troyan Municipality

In Troyan Municipality some of the most visited villages are Shipkovo, Chiflik, Oreshak and Cherni Osam.

In the village of Shipkovo are located the Shipkovo mineral baths. There are 24 accommodation establishments. Thanks to its warm mineral springs, the village

became known as a place for spa treatment during the Renaissance, and in the distant 1946 officially acquired the status of a resort. The village of Shipkovo stretches on the eastern slopes of Vasilyovska Mountain - the highest part of the foothills of Central Balkan Mountains. It is located in the valleys of the Small and Big rivers, which gather and form the river Ruzhdavets, flowing into the river Beli Osam flowing through the town of Troyan. The favorable geographical location (about 130 km from Plovdiv and 145 km from Sofia) makes it an easily accessible and attractive destination for mountain and spa tourism. On the territory of Shipkovo there are several mineral springs of different composition and purpose, with temperatures ranging from 180°C to 350°C. In the center there is a tap with four spouts, which is fed by springs L-28 (for the treatment of neurological and eye diseases), L-2 (for the treatment of gastric, kidney and liver diseases), mountain spring water and table mineral water. The resort offers several outdoor pools, some with hot mineral water. The village of Shipkovo offers a wide choice of accommodation establishments (small hotels, villas, holiday resorts and guest houses) and restaurants.

One of the emblematic holiday destinations in the municipality of Troyan, is the small village of Chiflik. It is located 14 km southwest of Troyan, at the source of the Beli Osam River and very quickly establishes itself as a spa complex of national importance. In addition to the opportunity for complete recreation in incredible nature and fresh air, in the village of Chiflik there are several hot mineral springs with temperatures up to 55°C. Their water is low mineralized, suitable for the treatment of diseases of the musculoskeletal system, allergic and endocrine diseases, as well as damage to the central and peripheral nervous system. Chiflik offers extremely good accommodation options - 23 establishments. Two of them are categorized with three stars. All large hotels, as well as some of the smaller ones, have indoor and outdoor swimming pools with mineral water. The resort has a large Olympic-sized outdoor pool located in the center of the village. From the village there are several wonderful routes leading to the territory of the Central Balkan National Park and its adjacent reserve Goat Wall. It is one of the few places in Europe where edelweiss still grows.

The villages of Oreshak and Cherni Osam are respectively 8 and 12 km away from the town of Troyan and about 180 km. from the capital Sofia. They are located in the so-called Troyan Balkan, part of the Central Balkan National Park. On the territory of the park rise two of the highest Balkan giants - the peaks Golyam Kupan (2169 m) and Levski (2166 m). At the foot of the second of them springs the river Cherni Osam. The biggest historical and cultural landmark in this area is the Troyan Monastery, which is one of the largest Bulgarian monasteries. It was founded in the late 16th century. It is famous for its miraculous icon "St. Virgin with three hands". A landmark in the village of Oreshak is the National Exhibition of Arts and Crafts, established in 1971. This is the only place in Bulgaria where masters from all over the country show their works. The village of Cherni Osam is famous with the Natural History Museum, located there. It presents over 700 plant and animal species typical of the Central Balkan Mountains. Since 2000, the museum has housed the

Information Center of the Central Balkan National Park. There are 33 accommodation establishments in the village of Oreshak and 17 in the village of Cherni Osam.

4.1.2. Teteven Municipality

In Teteven Municipality one of the most visited places is the village of Ribaritsa. It is located in the Teteven Mountains, at 600 m above sea level, at the foot of Mount Vezhen (2198 m), 12 km from Teteven and 124 km northeast of Sofia. In 1963 Ribaritsa was declared a mountain climate resort. Ribaritsa is a starting point for several hiking trails, such as the eco-trail to the Tsarichina Reserve. In the village can be rented bicycles and alpine bikes, ATVs, professional guides for hiking tours, the mountain is suitable for picnics, there are opportunities for fishing. In Ribaritsa there are 66 accommodation establishments. They are more than 50% of the total number of accommodation facilities in Teteven Municipality. The restaurants offer local and traditional Bulgarian cuisine. Detailed information about the opportunities for tourism in Ribaritsa and the region tourists can get at the Municipal Tourism Bureau in Teteven.

4.1.3. Apriltsi Municipality

Almost all accommodation establishment (125) in Apriltsi Municipality are located in the town of Apriltsi. It is located near the Central Balkan National Park and is the starting point for climbing Botev Peak and Vidimsko Praskalo Waterfall, which is one of the highest in Bulgaria.

4.1.4. Tourist service in Lovech Province

A total of 12 tour operators and travel agents are registered on the territory of Lovech Province. They are based in the municipal centers. Five of them are in rural areas - two in Troyan and one tour operator in Apriltsi, Lukovit and Ugarchin.

There are five tourist information centers in Lovech Province. Only one is located in the urban municipality of Lovech. There are two centers in Troyan, which give complete information to tourists about the region, offer 4 types of tourist maps of Troyan Municipality and the region of Central Balkan Mountains with GPS information. They also sell plane tickets, excursions, provide information on transport schedules, etc. There is one tourist information center in Lukovit and Teteven. The one in Lukovit provides on request a guide for the eco-trails and a boat trip.

The analysis of tourism in the rural areas in Lovech Province shows that the most attractive are the mountainous rural areas, settlements with mineral springs and rich cultural and historical heritage. The least developed is the tourism in the rural areas of Letnitsa and Ugarchin, which are located in the lower parts of the Fore-Balkans and the Danube Plain.

4.2. Tourism in the rural areas in Montana Province

Montana Province has an area of 3 636 sq. km. 81% (2 960 sq. km) of it is rural area. It includes 129 settlements: 8 cities and 121 villages. There are 11 municipalities - Berkovitsa, Boychinovtsi, Brusartsi, Chiprovtsi, Georgi Damyanovo, Lom, Medkovets, Montana, Vulchedrum, Varshets and Yakimovo. Only Montana is an urban municipality.

57 tourist attractions are registered in Montana Province. 17 of them are located in Berkovitsa Municipality. Some of the most famous architectural monuments of culture of national importance in Berkovitsa are the Church of the Nativity of the Blessed Virgin Mary, the Church of "St. Nicholas the Wonderworker" and "Ivan Vazov" House Museum. In Varshets Municipality there are 11 tourist attractions and a monument of culture - Klisura Monastery. In Lom Municipality there are 7 registered tourist attractions. The most famous are the city's historical museum and the ancient fortress Almus and Krastio Pishurka's house. All of them are of national importance. 7 registered tourist attractions are located in Medkovets Municipality. The most important is the cultural monument St. Paraskeva Temple. There are 5 tourist attractions in Vulchedrum Municipality. Some of them are the ancient Tsebrus Fortress, the Grapevine Mound and the ancient Kamistra Fortress. Five local landmarks are located on the territory of Chiprovtsi Municipality. The most important is the Catholic Cathedral of Santa Maria. In Georgi Damyanovo Municipality there are only 4 tourist attractions. A cultural monument there is the Lopushan Monastery. In Boychinovtsi the most important tourist attraction is the clock tower. It is immovable monument of culture of national importance (Varadzhakova, 2020).

In 2022 in the rural areas of Montana Province there are registered 85 accommodation establishments with total capacity of 1654 beds. These are over 4 times less than in Lovech Province. They are divided into 9 categories, whose territorial distribution by rural areas is shown in Fig. 4. It should be noted that in terms of population in rural areas, the two provinces - Montana and Lovech, have almost the same number of inhabitants - about 94 000. This means that the population in Lovech *зидэсхъе* is more engaged in tourism. In three municipalities (Vulchedrum, Medkovets and Yakimovo) there is not a single accommodation *объсвсшц*, and in the municipalities of Boychinovtsi, Brusartsi and Georgi Damyanovo only one. This data show that in 30% of the territory of Montana Province there are no accommodation establishments, and in 25% there is only one facility. In the municipalities of Lom and Chiprovtsi there are 9 accommodation establishments. 75% of the accommodation facilities in the province are in the municipalities of Varshets and Berkovitsa.

Fig. 4. Map of the rural areas in Montana Province

4.2.1. Varshets Municipality

Varshets Municipality is famous for the mineral springs in the town of Varshets and the village of Spanchevtsi. Varshets is the oldest spa resort in Bulgaria. It is located at the foot of the Western Balkan Mountains, 90 km from Sofia. The lack of limestone in the water of Varshets makes it one of the softest in Bulgaria, suitable for the treatment of many diseases. Varshets is also famous for its beautiful park, which is the second largest artificial park in Bulgaria after Boris's Garden in Sofia, with an area of 800 decares. Near the town (about 13 km) is the Klisura Monastery "Saints Cyril and Methodius", founded in the 13th century. From Varshets there is an eco-trail to the Balkan Mountains peak Todorini Kukli (1785 m). The tourist information center in the city offers a guide to the peak, as well as information about tourist sites and accommodation facilities. The high-category accommodation

establishments in the province are only two four-star hotels in Varshets – Medicus Hotel and the ATA Hotel. Every year in early August in Varshets is held a traditional fest of the resort, the mineral water and the Balkans. The village of Spanchevtsi is 2 km away from Varshets, and accommodation facilities are offered in the holiday spa complex Minkovi Bani Hotel.

4.2.2. Berkovitsa Municipality

Berkovitsa Municipality is located entirely in the Western Balkans and the Western Fore-Balkan. Kom Peak (2016 m) is located south of the town of Berkovitsa. From here starts one of the most attractive and longest mountain tourist route on the ridge of Balkans mountain Kom–Emine, with almost 600 km. length. The Kom ski area offers slopes and two modernly furnished teahouses. About 70% of the accommodation establishments in the municipality are in the town of Berkovitsa, and the rest in the villages of Barzia and Yagodovo.

4.2.3. Tourist service in Montana Province

Only 7 tour operators and travel agents are registered in the province. Two travel agents are registered in rural areas - in Berkovitsa EIM Travel Ltd. and in Lom Roden Kray - Agnesa Porozhanova. Only one tourist association, Asparuhov Hill (in the town of Lom), is registered on the territory of the province. There are two tourist information centers in Montana Province. They are located in Berkovitsa and in Varshets.

4.3. Tourism in the rural areas in Vidin Province

Vidin Province is the least populated in Bulgaria (40 p. / sq. km). The population density in its rural areas is about 12 p. / sq. km. It covers an area of 3032.9 sq. km. 85% (2557 sq. km.) of them are occupied by rural areas. It includes 11 municipalities - Belogradchik, Boynitsa, Bregovo, Vidin, Gramada, Dimovo, Kula, Makresh, Novo Selo, Ruzhintsi and Chuprene. Only Vidin Municipality is an urban one.

There are less than twice registered tourist attractions in the province compared to the other provinces in the region. They are only 35. There are 22 located in the rural municipalities. In Novo Selo Municipality there are 9. Some of the most important are the cultural monuments of national importance as the Roman castle Florentiana and the prehistoric and antique settlement Unio Alba. In Belogradchik Municipality there are 8 registered tourist attractions. The most important for tourism are the Magura Cave, Belogradchik Rocks and Kaleto Fortress. There are 2 registered tourist attractions in Dimovo Municipality. The most important one is the cave Venetsa in the village of Oreshets. In Gramada Municipality is the stone forest Chuturite, in Kula is the late antique Roman fortress Castro Martis and in the village of Rakovitsa in Makresh Municipality is the Holy Trinity Monastery, which is a cultural monument of national importance (Varadzhakova, 2020). There are two large caves in the area - Magurata and Venetsa. Magurata cave is famous for its

drawings of primitive people and numerous bats. In Venetsa Cave is built artistic color lighting, funded by a project of the EU program, which gives a spectacular view of the formations. The basic resource for water tourism in Vidin Province is mainly the Danube River. It is northern border of the province and with it borders Romania. The quality of water in port areas in the Bulgarian section is greatly influenced by human activity. The active reaction, dissolved oxygen, electrical conductivity, BOD5, ammonium and nitrite nitrogen are in the threshold values (Gartsiyanova, 2018).

In 2022 in the rural areas of Vidin Province there are 51 registered accommodation establishments with a total capacity of 614 beds. 40 of the accommodation facilities are in Belogradchik Municipality, 6 in Dimovo Municipality. In four municipalities (Boynitsa, Bregovo, Kula, and Makresh) there is no accommodation establishments, and in three municipalities (Gramada, Novo Selo and Ruzhintsi) there is only one. There are two accommodation facilities in Chuprene Municipality. The total area of rural zones without accommodation establishments is 13 500 sq. km, which is 35% of the rural areas territory in the province.

Fig. 5. Map of the rural areas in Vidin Province

4.3.1. Belogradchik Municipality

Belogradchik Municipality includes parts of the Western Fore-Balkans, the Western part of the Balkan Mountains and the southernmost part of the Western Danube Plain. There are five natural landmarks on this small area - Belogradchik rocks, Magurata cave, Bela Voda waterfall near the village of Stakevtsi, the Borov Kamak rock phenomenon near the village of Borovitsa and part of the Chuprene biosphere reserve. The air is very clear and the territory of the municipality offers wonderful opportunities for excursions and recreation, cycling, cave and congress tourism, mountaineering, hunting, fishing, sports and astronomical observations. Half of all accommodation establishments in the municipality are located in the town of Belogradchik, where is the only high-class hotel - the four-star hotel The Rocks. The rest accommodation facilities are concentrated in the villa zones Izvos and Markashnitsa, in the villages Borovitsa, Stakevtsi and Rabisha.

4.3.2. Dimovo Municipality

Dimovo Municipality is located in the Western Danube Plain and the Western Fore-Balkans. Prerequisites for the development of tourism in the municipality are the existing natural resources, geographical location and proximity to tourist sites of national and international importance. The area of the village of Gara Oreshets is rich in karst caves. Larger and easily accessible are the caves Venetsa and Kozarnika. In the area of the village of Archar is located the archeological site Ratsiaria, with remains of the Roman city Ratsiaria, which dates back to the beginning of the first century AD. It was a military center on the northern border of Mizia Province. 2 km south of the village of Izvor is the Monastery "St. Mother of God".

There are 6 accommodation establishments in the municipality. Four of them are registered in the village of Yanyovets. It is located only 7 km. from Belogradchik in the Venetsa mountain hill and has a population of only 17 people.

4.3.3. Tourist service in Vidin Province

In the rural areas of Vidin Province there are one tour operator registered in Belogradchik and one travel agent in Kula with office in Vidin. There are only one tourist association registered on the territory of the province - the Belogradchik Rocks Tourist Association in Belogradchik. There are tourist information centers in Belogradchik, Kula and Chuprene.

4.4. Tourism in the rural areas in Vratsa Province

Vratsa Province covers 3 620 sq. Km. 72% (2615 sq. km) of its territory is rural areas. Vratsa Province includes a total of 123 settlements. 8 of them are cities. The municipalities included in this province are: Borovan, Byala Slatina, Hayredin, Kozloduy, Krivodol, Mezdra, Mizia, Oryahovo, Roman and Vratsa. Only Vratsa is an urban municipality.

There are 67 registered tourist attractions in the province. Forty of them are located in rural areas. The most attractive are the treasure from the Mogilan mound,

the silver treasure from the village of Rogozen, the Botev Road Memorial Complex and the Ledenika Amusement Park. Vrachanski Balkan Natural Park is a protected area. In Borovan Municipality there are 18 military monuments and museums. Byala Slatina Municipality is attractive with the prehistoric settlement in the Drashan cave. There are 7 tourist attractions in Kozloduy Municipality. Some of the most attractive for the tourists are the place where Botev's detachment descends and the ancient fortress Augusta. Mezdra Municipality has five registered tourist attractions. Some of them are the archeological complex Kaleto and the Cherepish Monastery "Uspenie Bogorodichno". In Mizia Municipality, in the village of Sofronievo there is a center for artistic crafts. In Roman Municipality there are six registered tourist attractions. The fortress Krivgrad is a cultural monument of national importance. In Oryahovo Municipality there are 8 tourist attractions, where the medieval Kamaka Fortress is of national importance (Varadzhakova, 2020).

The archeological and historical tourist resources and the significant treasures discovered in Vratsa Province define the tourist profile of this destination and make it proper for cultural and historical tourism.

There are 5 sites in the rural areas of the province, which are included in the list of The 100 National Tourist Sites of the Bulgarian Tourism Union. These are Kaleto Archaeological Complex in Mezdra, Ledenika Cave, the National Steamboat Radetski Museum and the monument of Hristo Botev and his detachment and Okolchitsa Peak.

In 2022 in the rural areas of Vratsa district there are 41 registered accommodation establishments with a total capacity of 765 beds. There are no accommodation facilities in the municipalities of Hayredin and Mizia, and only one in Borovan and Roman. In Byala Slatina Municipality there are two, and in the municipalities of Krivodol and Oryahovo there are four accommodation establishments. 19 of the accommodation facilities are in Mezdra Municipality and 10 in Kozloduy Municipality. 80% of the beds in the province are registered in these two municipalities.

Fig. 6. Map of the rural areas in Vratsa Province

4.4.1. Mezdra Municipality

Mezdra Municipality covers the northern part of Iskar Gorge and the Fore-Balkans. The relief is flat-hilly and semi-mountainous. The main landmarks are the Iskar Gorge, the Cherepish Monastery and the Kaletto Fortress.

Natural and historical landmarks, white rocks of the majestic Iskar gorge attractive and challenging for climbers offer rich opportunities for cultural tourism, hiking, mountaineering, paragliding and hang gliding. In the village of Lyutibrod, on the west bank of the river Iskar flowing through it, the unique rock formations Ritlite rise. They are attractive for alpinists and climbers.

The historic Rashov Dol, where ten Botev rebels were killed and where the bones of heroic Bulgarians are kept in a small tomb is an antropoghenic tourist resource. In this area is the Cherepish Monastery, which is a cultural monument of national importance. It was founded during the Second Bulgarian State, during the reign of Tsar Ivan Shishman (1371-1393).

Near the town of Mezdra on the banks of Iskar River, on the remains of the Chalcolithic era, the ancient and medieval fortress Kaleto was discovered. There are well-preserved remains of the fortress walls and houses from the end of the 14th century.

Over 70% of the beds in the accommodation establishments are in the villages in the mountainous rural areas - Zverino, Lyutibrod, Ochindol and Tipchenitsa. The Oasis complex, which includes a hotel and guest houses, is the only accommodation facility with a higher category - three stars. It is located only 90 km. from Sofia.

4.4.2. Kozloduy Municipality

The relief of the municipality is flat, as most of its territory is occupied by the eastern part of the vast loess plateau Zlatiyata. The main waterway is the Danube river, which borders Romania to the north. Along the border with Mizia Municipality passes the lower reaches of Ogosta river, which flows through the lands of the villages of Kriva bara, Boutan, Glozhene and Harlets. The main part of the territory of the municipality is occupied by agricultural lands.

In Kozloduy Municipality there are 10 accommodation establishments with a total of 182 beds – the most for Vratsa Province. All facilities are in the town of Kozloduy. These are two hotels, three pensions and five guest houses. In Kozloduy Municipality, the tourist activity is more related to providing opportunities for recreation and entertainment for those living in its territory. There are two main tourist hikes, the route of which passes through the municipality - the national tourist hike “in the footsteps of the Botev detachment - Kozloduy-Okolchitsa” and the international water hike on the Danube.

4.4.3. Tourist service in Vratsa Province

The tourist service in the rural areas of Vratsa Province is at a very low level. There is no functioning tour operator or travel agency. Only one tourist information center is registered in the town of Oryahovo. Also in Oryahovo there is one registered tourist association, Tourist Association Radetski – 99.

4.5. Tourism in the rural areas in Pleven Province

Pleven Province has an area of 4 337 sq. km. 85% (3 944 sq. km) of its territory is occupied by rural areas. It includes 123 settlements - 14 cities and 109 villages. It is divided into 11 municipalities - Belene, Cherven Bryag, Dolni Dabnik, Dolna Mitropolia, Gulyantsi, Iskar, Kneja, Levski, Nikopol, Pleven, Pordim. Only Pleven is an urban municipality.

Pleven Province, including its rural areas, is rich in historical and cultural monuments. There are 66 registered tourist attractions. Nikopol Municipality has the largest number - 28 churches and immovable cultural monuments. In Gulyantsi Municipality there are 13. The Ulpia Escus Archaeological Reserve is the most important one. In Levski Municipality there are 8 sites, in Knezha - 5, in Dolna Mitropolia - 4. The Roman station Ad Putea, near the village of Riben, has national

importance. There are 3 tourist attractions in the municipalities of Cherven Bryag and Belene. The most important one, called national cultural monument, is the Roman castle Dimum. In Pordim Municipality there are two state museums (Varadzhakova, 2020).

In Pleven Province there are 16 registered accommodation establishments located in rural areas. In all municipalities there are from 1 to 3 accommodation facilities, and in two municipalities - Gulyantsi and Pordim there is none.

Fig. 7. Map of the rural areas in Plevan Province

Outside the urban municipality of Plevan there is a registered travel agent only in Belene.

5. Conclusion

As a result of the study of rural areas in the North-West Region, few main conclusions can be drawn. First, the accommodation establishments are concentrated in areas with mountainous terrain, where the air is clean, the nature offers opportunities for different types of mountain tourism - walking on eco-trails, climbing peaks, rock climbing, riding ATVs and bicycles, etc.

Second, the arrivals in rural areas with mineral springs is higher. There the accommodation facilities have a higher category. They offer spa treatments,

swimming in outdoor and indoor pools and relaxing in mountain and semi-mountainous conditions.

Third, rural areas in the plains are not subject to tourism. There are no accommodation establishments in the villages. In the rural areas cities with large industrial enterprises, there are accommodation facilities that are used primarily for business and congress tourism.

Fourth, in the rural areas, tourist services are very low in quality. Just in few of them of them there are travel agencies or tourist information centers. As a result, advertising and promotion of these destinations are very weak.

In conclusion, the findings can be used by local and national authorities in developing strategies and plans for rural development in the field of tourism.

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